

Mixed ligand complexes of molybdenum(0) and tungsten(0) containing Mannich bases and carbonyl as ligands

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Abstract : Mixed ligand carbonyl complexes of molybdenum and tungsten of composition, $[M(\text{CO})(\text{L-L})]$, (where M = Mo or W and L-L = morpholinobenzyl benzamide (MBB), piperidinobenzyl benzamide (PBB), piperidinobenzyl urea (PBU), piperidinobenzyl thiourea (PBTU), morpholinobenzyl urea (MBU) and morpholinobenzyl thiourea (MBTU)) are reported. Complexes of molybdenum have been prepared by refluxing molybdenum hexacarbonyl and the ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio in 50 cm³ of xylene for 10–12 h whereas for tungsten complexes, tungsten hexacarbonyl and the ligands in 1 : 1 ratio were refluxed in 50 cm³ of tetrahydrofuran for 7–8 h. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Vis, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, conductivity measurements and magnetic susceptibility. The CO force constants and CO-CO interaction constants for these derivatives have been calculated using Cotton-Kraihanzel secular equations, which indicate poor π -bonding ability of the coordinated ligands. ¹³C NMR and electronic spectral data show loss of *cis*-carbonyl ligands and formation of *cis*-disubstituted tetracarbonyl derivatives of molybdenum and tungsten. Finally, the free ligands and their metal complexes were tested *in vitro* against some pathogenic bacteria to assess their antimicrobial properties.

Keywords : Mannich bases, Cotton-Kraihanzel secular equations, bidentate ligands, molybdenum, tungsten, force constants.

Introduction

The chemistry of metal carbonyls has been of considerable interest for several decades mainly due to structural aspects and reactivity of these compounds in respect to several classes of organic ligands, and also by their interesting application in catalysis and in electronic devices based on non-linear optical effects^{1–4}. The photochemistry of tungsten carbonyl complexes $[M(\text{CO})_x \text{L}_{6-x}]$ has been receiving great attentions⁵. A number of derivatives of tungsten carbonyl complexes, *cis*- $[\text{W}(\text{CO})_4(\text{L-L})]$ containing diimine ligands (L-L = 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, 1,4-diazabutadiene and pyridylamine Schiff base) have been reported^{6–10}. Tungsten carbonyl complexes derived from the dianions of 2-aminophenol and 1,2-diaminobenzene stabilized by π -donation from the amido groups of chelating ligands have also been reported¹¹.

Reaction of Schiff bases (SB) namely, 1,2-bis(4-methylbenzylideneimine)propane; 1,2-bis(4-methoxybenzylideneimine)propane; 1,2-bis(4-*N,N*-dimethylamino-

benzylideneimine)propane; 1,2-bis(4-methylacetophenoneimine)propane and 1,2-bis(4-methoxyacetophenoneimine)propane with $\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$ gives *cis*- $[(\text{SB})\text{W}(\text{CO})_4]$. Halogen oxidation of these *cis*-disubstituted products has also been carried out with Cl_2 , which invariably displaced all the CO groups to give $[(\text{SB})\text{WCl}_4]$ ¹². 2-Thiouracilate and 6-methyl-2-thiouracilate derivatives of tungsten carbonyl have been synthesized from the reaction of photogenerated $\text{W}(\text{CO})_5(\text{solvent})$ (solvent = MeOH or THF) and corresponding $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]$ [thiouracilate]¹³.

Novel orotic acid derivatives of tungsten carbonyl, $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{W}(\text{CO})_4(\text{orotate})]$, $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{W}(\text{CO})_4(\text{dihydroorotate})]$ [where orotate = $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)^{2-}$, dihydroorotate = $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)^{2-}$] have been reported and found to be O,N-ligated complexes^{14,15}. A number of phosphine tetracarbonyl halide salts of group VI metals of the type *cis*- $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{PR}_3\text{M}(\text{CO})_4\text{X}]$ [where $\text{PR}_3 = (p\text{-FC}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$ or $(p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{P}$, M = Cr or Mo for X = Cl] have been synthesized and characterized¹⁶.

Schiff's bases with bi- and tridentate pyridine-bis(imine) ligands have been the focus of current research in polymer science for the polymerization of ethylene and propylene^{17,18}. The catalytic properties of long chain Schiff base complexes of tetracarbonylmolybdenum(0) for the free radical polymerization of methyl methacrylate were also studied¹⁹. Four new dinuclear molybdenum tetracarbonyl complexes with tetradentate nitrogen ligands have been synthesized and spectroscopically characterized. The intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the crystal structure of *N,N'*-bis-[1-(pyridine-2-yl)ethylidene]ethane-1,2-diamine has also been studied²⁰. In this paper we describe the synthesis and characterization of *cis*-disubstituted molybdenum and tungsten carbonyl complexes containing benzaldehyde based Mannich base ligands. The structures of ligands are given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic results (Tables 1-3) showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with general formula *cis*-[(L-L)M(CO)₄], where M = Mo or W and L-L = MBB, PBB, MBU, PBU, MBTU and PBTU. All the complexes are coloured, air stable having characteristic melting points and are soluble in DMF, DMSO,

xylene and THF but insoluble in *n*-hexane and petroleum ether.

Conductance and magnetic measurements :

The observed molar conductance of molybdenum complexes in xylene (10^{-3} M) and tungsten complexes in THF (10^{-3} M) are in the range 19.68 – $29.43 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and 17.64 – $30.11 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively which indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for low spin molybdenum(0) and tungsten(0) complexes.

Infrared spectra :

Metal to carbon monoxide bonding in metal carbonyls involves combination of C→M dative sigma-bond with M→C dative pi-bonding. The CO force constants and CO-CO interaction constants for these derivatives have been calculated using Cotton-Kraihanzel secular equations²¹.

$$2A_1 \begin{vmatrix} \mu(k_2 + 2k_i) - \lambda & 2\mu k_i \\ 2\mu k_i & \mu(k_1 + k_i) - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$B_1 \lambda = \mu (k_2 - 2k_i) \quad (2)$$

$$B_2 \lambda = \mu (k_1 - 2k_i) \quad (3)$$

In these equations, k_1 = stretching force constant for CO groups *trans* to ligands, k_2 = stretching force constant for CO groups *cis* to ligands, k_i = CO-CO interaction force constant, μ = reciprocal of reduced mass of CO (0.14583) and $A = (5.8890 \times 10^{-2} \text{ v}^2)$, where ν = frequency in cm^{-1} and the force constants are in dynes cm^{-1} .

All complexes show four CO stretching bands in the infrared region 2065 – 1822 cm^{-1} due to $2A_1 + B_1 + B_2$ modes as expected for C_{2v} symmetry and in agreement with their *cis*-configuration²¹. The frequencies for the complexes of unsymmetrical ligands are assigned as follows. The higher frequency A_1 and B_1 bands are assigned to *trans*-carbonyl ligands, while the lower frequency A_1 and B_2 bands are assigned to *cis*-carbonyl ligands.

The values of k_1 , k_2 and k_i for molybdenum complexes were found in the ranges 13.70 – 13.91 , 15.67 – 16.01 and 0.28 – 0.32 mdynes/\AA respectively, whereas for tungsten complexes the values of k_1 , k_2 and k_i were found in the ranges 14.18 – 14.55 , 15.85 – 16.15 and 0.24 – 0.29 mdynes/\AA respectively, which confirm the validity of vibrational mode assignments. The values of CO stretching

Table 1. Analytical data and some physical properties of the synthesized complexes of the type $[M(CO)_4(L-L)]$

Sl. no.	Complex/Empirical formula (Mol. wt.) g/mol	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	S	M
1.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBB]$	Yellow	131	2.24 (2.38)	3.90 (3.96)	5.50 (5.55)	-	19.01 (19.04)
	$MoC_{22}H_{20}N_2O_6$ (504)							
2.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBB]$	Light orange	129	54.91 (54.98)	4.27 (4.38)	5.55 (5.57)	-	19.08 (19.12)
	$MoC_{23}H_{22}N_2O_5$ (502)							
3.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBU]$	Light yellow	138	46.21 (46.25)	3.79 (3.85)	9.46 (9.52)	-	21.69 (21.76)
	$MoC_{17}H_{19}N_3O_5$ (441)							
4.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBTU]$	Light orange	140	44.57 (44.63)	3.61 (3.71)	9.11 (9.19)	6.96 (7.00)	20.94 (21.00)
	$MoC_{17}H_{19}N_3O_4S$ (457)							
5.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBU]$	Light yellow	134	43.26 (43.34)	3.54 (3.61)	9.35 (9.48)	-	21.56 (21.67)
	$MoC_{16}H_{17}N_3O_6$ (443)							
6.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBTU]$	Yellow	135	41.77 (41.83)	3.42 (3.48)	9.08 (9.19)	6.90 (6.97)	20.90 (20.91)
	$MoC_{16}H_{17}N_3O_5S$ (459)							
7.	$[W(CO)_4MBB]$	Light yellow	129	44.52 (44.59)	3.68 (3.71)	4.70 (4.72)	-	30.94 (31.08)
	$WC_{22}H_{20}N_2O_6$ (592)							
8.	$[W(CO)_4PBB]$	Light yellow	124	46.74 (46.77)	3.68 (3.72)	4.70 (4.74)	-	31.04 (31.11)
	$WC_{23}H_{22}N_2O_5$ (590)							
9.	$[W(CO)_4PBU]$	Crimson	128	38.51 (38.56)	3.54 (3.59)	7.90 (7.93)	-	34.74 (34.78)
	$WC_{17}H_{19}N_3O_5$ (529)							
10.	$[W(CO)_4PBTU]$	Light orange	139	37.40 (37.43)	3.44 (3.48)	7.67 (7.70)	5.82 (5.81)	33.72 (33.76)
	$WC_{17}H_{19}N_3O_4S$ (545)							
11.	$[W(CO)_4MBU]$	Light yellow	130	36.12 (36.15)	3.18 (3.20)	7.86 (7.90)	-	34.60 (34.65)
	$WC_{16}H_{17}N_3O_6$ (531)							
12.	$[W(CO)_4MBTU]$	Yellow	141	35.08 (35.10)	3.07 (3.10)	7.62 (7.67)	5.81 (5.87)	33.72 (33.76)
	$WC_{16}H_{17}N_3O_5S$ (547)							

Table 2. Electronic spectral data (nm) of *cis*- $[M(CO)_4(L-L)]$ complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	λ_{max}	
		(<i>d</i> - π^* CO transition)	(<i>d</i> - <i>d</i> transition)
1.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBB]$	368, 375, 396	477
2.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBB]$	374, 387, 407	479
3.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBU]$	369, 383, 398	458
4.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBTU]$	367, 381, 410	481
5.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBU]$	372, 388, 417	456
6.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBTU]$	370, 386, 412	489
7.	$[W(CO)_4MBB]$	362, 375, 389	467
8.	$[W(CO)_4PBB]$	364, 374, 390	472
9.	$[W(CO)_4PBU]$	366, 376, 388	458
10.	$[W(CO)_4PBTU]$	361, 373, 389	471
11.	$[W(CO)_4MBU]$	367, 378, 390	469
12.	$[W(CO)_4MBTU]$	362, 376, 387	459

Table 3. ^{13}C NMR data for the carbonyl ligands in $[M(CO)_4(L-L)]$ complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	^{13}C resonance, ppm		
		CO (axial)	CO (<i>trans</i> to S or N)	CO (<i>trans</i> to N)
1.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBB]$	202.7	213.7	214.9
2.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBB]$	201.9	213.9	214.6
3.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBU]$	204.5	215.8	216.3
4.	$[Mo(CO)_4PBTU]$	202.8	217.1	218.2
5.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBU]$	203.9	213.9	215.1
6.	$[Mo(CO)_4MBTU]$	204.4	216.1	217.3
7.	$[W(CO)_4MBB]$	200.6	214.3	214.7
8.	$[W(CO)_4PBB]$	200.9	214.9	215.3
9.	$[W(CO)_4PBU]$	203.9	216.4	216.8
10.	$[W(CO)_4PBTU]$	203.5	217.5	217.8
11.	$[W(CO)_4MBU]$	204.4	215.8	216.3
12.	$[W(CO)_4MBTU]$	203.6	216.9	217.2

force constants in the complexes are lower than that for $Mo(CO)_6$ (16.52 mdynes/Å) and $W(CO)_6$ (16.41 mdynes/Å) indicating the replacement of two CO groups by the

ligand (L-L) and poor pi-bonding ability of the ligands used^{22,23}. These values are close to the values of force

constants deduced for other nitrogen containing *cis*-disubstituted group VI metal carbonyls^{24,25}.

However, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ absorption band at 1610–1650 cm^{-1} in the free ligands MBB, PBB, MBU and PBU and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ modes of MBTU and PBTU at 1290–1295 cm^{-1} are lowered by 20–30 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen (O) or thiocarbonyl sulphur (S) in bonding with metal. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C})$ mode of morpholine and piperidine ring around 1115–1130 cm^{-1} show a negative shift in the complexes indicating the involvement of ring nitrogen in bonding with molybdenum. A slight positive shift in (C–O–C) stretching mode of morpholine ring shows that morpholine ring does not involve its oxygen atom in bond formation with metal.

These IR bands suggest that in all the complexes the ligands behave in bidentate chelating mode coordinating the metal through carbonyl (O) or thiocarbonyl (S) and the ring nitrogen.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of mixed ligands carbonyl derivatives of the type *cis*-[M(CO)₄(L-L)] (M = Cr, Mo, W and L-L = a bidentate nitrogen ligand) have been extensively studied by Stufkens and collaborators^{26,27}. The absorption spectra of complexes were measured in DMSO. The electronic spectra (Table 2) display three bands in the range 367–417 nm and 361–390 nm for molybdenum and tungsten complexes respectively due to complexation and a weak band in the range of 456–489 nm and 458–472 nm. The three bands are attributed to *d*- π^* CO transitions whereas the weak band is due to *d*-*d* transitions.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the representative ligand, morpholinobenzyl urea (MBU) was recorded in deuterated methanol. The spectrum shows a triplet at δ 3.42 ppm for N-CH₂ of morpholine ring. The methylidyne proton of Ph-CH-NH appears as a septet at δ 7.97 ppm. In the complex [Mo(CO)₄MBU], the peaks corresponding to four protons of -CH₂ groups of N-CH₂ in piperidine ring undergo downfield shift with δ 4.08 ppm. This is due to coordination of ring nitrogen of morpholine with molybdenum. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the representative ligand, piperidinobenzyl urea (PBU) was recorded in deuterated methanol. The spectrum shows a triplet at δ 3.55 ppm for N-CH₂ of piperidine ring. The methylidyne proton of Ph-CH-NH appears as a septet at δ 7.65 ppm.

In the complex [W(CO)₄PBU], the peaks corresponding to four protons of -CH₂ groups of N-CH₂ in piperidine ring undergo downfield shift with δ 3.75 ppm. This is due to coordination of ring nitrogen of piperidine with tungsten.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectra of complexes in DMSO (Table 3) display three signals for the carbonyl carbons in an approximate 2 : 1 : 1 intensity ratio. An intense resonance is for two *cis* CO's and one for each of the other two CO's, *trans* to ring nitrogen and *trans* to oxygen or sulphur. Both of these later resonances are slightly downfield (assigned to CO groups *trans* to coordinated nitrogen and oxygen or sulphur) from the more intense resonance for the two *cis* CO ligands. The ¹³C signals are assigned on the basis that, ¹³C chemical shifts of the CO ligands for the more electrons donating O,N-ligated complexes are further downfield than the corresponding parameters for the S,N-ligated derivatives²⁸.

Antibacterial study :

The test solutions were prepared by dissolving the ligands in ethanol and the complexes in DMSO. In a typical procedure, discs of filter paper were dipped into the solution of each chemical separately for two hours. Seeded petriplates were then prepared by pouring in each petriplate, the nutrient agar medium followed by inoculation of bacterial suspension. After the solidification of the medium, the discs of chemicals were put on seeded plates and the plates were incubated at 25 °C for 48 h. During this period, the test solution was diffused and the growth of the inoculated microorganisms was affected. The inhibition zone (clear area around the disc) developed on each plate was measured (Fig. 1). The work was carried out under aseptic conditions and a standard antibiotic Rifampicin was used as the control here.

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of the ligands and their complexes at 300 ppm

Sl. no.	Compd.	Zone of inhibition in mm	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
1.	MBB	6.0	6.0
2.	MBTU	8.2	9.3
3.	[W(CO) ₄ MBB]	10	10
4.	[W(CO) ₄ MBTU]	16	14
5.	[Mo(CO) ₄ MBB]	13	18
6.	[Mo(CO) ₄ MBTU]	14	19
7.	Rifampicin	0.0	0.0

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity of the ligands and complexes.

It is evident from the antibacterial screening data (Table 4) that the metal complexes are more potent than the parent ligands. The chelation theory accounts for the increased activity of the metal complexes. Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups, thereby, increasing the lipophilic nature of the central atom which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layer of the cell membrane.

Based on physico-chemical and spectral studies, it is proposed that these complexes are mononuclear with composition, $[M(CO)(L-L)]$ having *cis*-configuration, where $M = Mo$ or W and $L-L = MBB, PBB, MBU, PBU, MBTU$ and $PBTU$. IR studies of these complexes reveal that ligands are coordinating with the central metal (Mo or W) in bidentate chelating mode through carbonyl oxygen (O) or thiocarbonyl sulphur (S) and the ring nitrogen of morpholine, piperidine of the corresponding ligands. In 1H NMR spectrum, the peaks corresponding to four protons of $-CH_2$ groups of $N-CH_2$ in piperidine ring and $O-CH_2$ in morpholine ring in case of complexes undergo downfield shift. This may be due to coordination of ring nitrogen of piperidine/morpholine with metal (Mo or W). Electronic and ^{13}C NMR studies reveal a *cis*-disubsti-

tuted product. Magnetic studies reveal diamagnetic nature which confirms low spin d^6 configuration of metal (Mo or W) in zero oxidation state. Molar conductance values indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. On the basis of these facts, following structure is proposed for these complexes.

Proposed structure for $[M(CO)_4MBU]$ ($M = Mo$ or W).

Experimental

Reagents and reaction conditions :

Morpholine (Fluka) and piperidine (SDS) were purified by distillation after keeping these bases over potas-

sium hydroxide overnight. Urea (Merck), thiourea (Ranbaxy), benzaldehyde (Qualigens), THF (Ranbaxy), tungsten hexacarbonyl (Aldrich) and molybdenum hexacarbonyl (Aldrich) were used as supplied. The ligands were prepared by reported method^{29,30}. All reactions were carried out under dry conditions in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The analysis of molybdenum and tungsten was carried out gravimetrically by reported method³¹. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were analyzed micro-analytically using CHNS analyzer Leco make model-932. Molar conductivity in DMF at room temperature was measured by Elico conductivity bridge type CM82T having conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.90. IR spectra of complexes over the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} were recorded on FT-IR spectrophotometer Vector-22 using KBr disc. Electronic spectra were run in DMSO on Beckman Du-6 spectrophotometer in the 190 to 800 nm range. ^1H NMR spectra were obtained in methanol and DMSO on a Bruker DRX 300 (120 MHz) using TMS as reference peak. ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker spectrometer with reference to residual solvent peaks with respect to TMS. Magnetic measurement at room temperature were carried out by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant.

Preparation of $[\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_4(\text{L-L})]$:

$\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$ (0.792 g, 3 mmol) and the ligand (3 mmol) : MBB (0.886 g), PBB (0.883 g), PBU (0.699 g), PBTU (0.747 g), MBU (0.705 g) and MBTU (0.753 g) were refluxed in 50 cm^3 of xylene for about 10–12 h under dry conditions in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The yellow solution obtained in each case was allowed to cool down and the yellow-orange air stable solid was obtained by evaporating the solvent *in vacuo*. After evaporation of volatiles, the residue is dissolved in minimum amount of xylene : dichloromethane (5 : 2) and left to stand for two days for crystallization at 223 K. The solvent was decanted and the light yellow crystals were dried *in vacuo* (yield : 65–80%).

Preparation of $[\text{W}(\text{CO})_4(\text{L-L})]$:

$\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$ (1.05 g, 3 mmol) and the ligand (3 mmol) : MBB (0.886 g), PBB (0.883 g), PBU (0.699 g), PBTU (0.747 g), MBU (0.705 g) and MBTU (0.753 g) were refluxed in 50 cm^3 of THF for about 7–8 h under dry

conditions in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The yellow solution obtained in each case was allowed to cool down and the yellow-orange air stable solid was obtained by evaporating the solvent *in vacuo*. Unreacted reactants were removed by washing the residue several times with *n*-hexane. The product was recrystallized in THF (yield : 60–70%).

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Sharma *et al.* : Mixed ligand complexes of molybdenum(0) and tungsten(0) *etc.*

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